

A REVIEW ON WET LITTER INDUCED PROBLEMS IN POULTRY

Chethan S^{1*}, Mohammad Azamthulla²

¹ Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, M. S. Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences, MSR Nagar, Bangalore, India -560054

² Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Pharmacy, M. S. Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences, MSR Nagar, Bangalore, India -560054

Abstract:

The deep litter system is important for the health, comfort, welfare and productivity of the birds. Litter materials (wood shavings, sawdust, peanut hulls, and rice husk) are frequently mixed with spilled food, feathers, and bird faeces to prevent infection in the poultry house. It functions as a moisture absorber, when the moisture content of chicken droppings (watery/loose) increases due to heavy water intake, the moisture-absorbing capacity of litter is totally saturated. As a result, water addition exceeds water removal (evaporation), resulting in litter moisture problems in chicken shelters. Wet litter is a complicated problem caused by a number of interconnected factors, including bird management and housing, disease and diet control, and gut health. It is also one of the most important factors in the development of footpad lesions (FPLs), also known as footpad dermatitis (FPD), which has become a major problem in recent years. Wet droppings can be effectively corrected by recognising the underlying causes, proper drinker management and shed ventilation would prevent difficulties caused by environmental or housing conditions. Similarly, using antibiotics at subtherapeutic doses reduces the prevalence of coccidiosis and necrotic enteritis infection. There are many problems associated with wet litter in the poultry, there are many herbs used in managing wet droppings. Indian medicinal herbs have traditionally been used to treat diarrhoea. Several literatures suggest that these can be used to prevent wet litter in the poultry. The present review highlights the causative factors, prevention and treatment of wet litter associated problems in the poultry.

Keywords: Broiler chickens, Poultry, Wet litter, Wet droppings, Footpad dermatitis

Introduction:

Litter is made up of the bedding materials (e.g., pine shavings, wood products, rice hulls, or peanut shells) and excreta. Broilers are typically housed on litter, which is mostly made up of bedding material such as wood shavings that is constantly mixed with feed, feathers, and excreta throughout the developing phase. [1]

Because the birds are constantly in contact with the litter, the litter's condition must be monitored to ensure a safe and comfortable environment. Litter has several functions, one of which is to absorb and store water from excreta and drinking system spillage until the water evaporates and is removed from the shed by the ventilation system. [2]

Litter moisture concentrations in fact range from 15 to 45 %, depending on the season. Depending on the type of material utilised, litter can absorb a significant amount of moisture. Wet litter is found to possess moisture content of more than 25% and a reduced cushioning, insulating, and water-holding capacity. "Wet litter" occurs when the amount of water deposited exceeds the amount of water removed by evaporation. Wet litter is a multifactorial problem. [3]

Wet litter is a collective term for wet and/or caked litter, which is frequently related to a variety of bird health, welfare, and environmental issues. Digestive upset, nutritional imbalance, diseases, drinking spills, insufficient ventilation, drinker management/ maintenance, humid weather, in-shed condensation, and inadequate litter water storage capability are just a few of the factors that might cause wet litter. The key factors influencing the occurrence of wet litter are bird management and housing, disease control, dietary considerations, and gut health. [4]

Wet litter has been connected to contact dermatitis in the poultry and has been shown to reduce feed conversion ratio and carcass yields. Diet/nutrition considerations, shed design, ventilation management, environmental conditions, and/or flock infections with organisms such as *Clostridium perfringens*, the causative agent of necrotic enteritis, can all lead to wet litter. [5]

Excessive water consumption has been associated to the occurrence of wet droppings. Heat stress in birds can be caused by high indoor temperatures and humidity, causing them to drink more and eat less in an attempt to control their body temperature. [5]

If birds take too much potassium, magnesium, sodium, sulphate, or chloride in their meal or water, it might result in wet droppings as they try to maintain their electrolyte balance. Furthermore, feed ingredients high in Non-Starch Polysaccharides (NSP), such as wheat, barley, and rye, are usually associated to wetter and more viscous excreta because these components trap water and prevent it from being reabsorbed. [6]

It is usual practice to utilise commercially available NSP-degrading enzyme preparations in diets rich in these feed ingredients. Ammonia volatilization, which can decrease air quality and is one of the most serious negative factors influencing bird productivity today, it is also caused by poor litter quality. Footpad dermatitis can be prevented by reducing the amount of moisture in the litter (FPD). [7]

Footpad dermatitis (FPD) is a multifactorial condition that causes dermatitis lesions on poultry footpads. Footpad dermatitis can also be referred to as pododermatitis or contact dermatitis. All of these terms refer to a condition characterised by inflammation and necrotic lesions on the plantar surface of the footpads and toes that range from superficial to deep. When serious ulcers develop, these lesions can cause discomfort and pain. Abscesses and thickening of the underlying tissues and structure can result from deep ulcers. [8]

FPD development requires a critical litter moisture content of about 35%, with FPD linearly increasing as litter moisture concentrations rise. To avoid production losses and maintain animal health and welfare, the poultry industry is focusing majorly on preventing wet litter. [9]

The quality of chicken meat excreta is affected by nutritional disturbances, which can be improved by managing microbial phytase and dietary electrolyte balance in the feed. [10]

Similarly, administering antibiotics at subtherapeutic doses reduces the occurrence of coccidiosis and necrotic enteritis infection, which is the most commonly mentioned of the diseases in concern. However, as a result of the ban on in-feed antibiotics and zinc oxide, well-known anti-diarrheal agents in piglets, animal health has deteriorated in European countries with increased loose droppings/diarrhoea due to gut disturbances, weight loss, and high mortality of early post-weaning pigs and broilers. [11]

Therefore, there is a need for natural alternatives to prevent the wet droppings. There are many traditional drugs like *Punica granatum*, *Acacia nilotica*, *Holarrhena antidysenterica* etc., which are used in the management of diarrheal disorders. [12]

Magnesium model to evaluate wet litter

Numerous models are available to evaluate wet litter problems in broiler chickens. One of them is that the addition of minerals in the diet at high doses can induce loose droppings/diarrhoea in broilers by altering osmolarity and water reabsorption in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), but the effect varies depending on individual minerals.

Magnesium is frequently employed as a laxative in humans and as an osmotic agent in animal diarrhoea models, with 2g/kg magnesium sulphate ($MgSO_4$) consistently induces diarrhoea in rats. Increasing dietary MgO levels in broilers, there is a dose-related reduction in gut digesta transit time. $MgSO_4$ is poorly absorbed in the intestine, causing alterations in osmotic pressure in the lumen and aquaporin 3 expression in rats. Reabsorption of water from the digesta is prevented due to decreased water transport by aquaporin 3 and as a result, more moisture is excreted.

In broilers, high levels of Mg have a negative effect on bone calcification and cause diarrhoea. Mg is absorbed mostly by the duodenum, ileum, and colon. In chickens, the gut passage absorbs 72 % of the dietary $MgSO_4$ intake.

Mg bioavailability is determined by the source of Mg, which has been demonstrated for both organic and inorganic Mg sources, as well as the ion dissociation in the intestine. Mg and SO_4 are both poorly utilised ions. As a result, choosing a different Mg source to include in broiler diets may be more appropriate.

Magnesium oxide (MgO) and magnesium chloride ($MgCl_2$) are less harmful and regarded to be less laxative than magnesium sulphate ($MgSO_4$). Mg may be used as a wet litter model in broilers, increasing excreta moisture by reducing water reabsorption in contrast to increased water consumption, in addition to its nutritional effects. [12,13]

Causative factors associated with wet litter

Management Causes

Excessive water consumption is linked to the occurrence of wet droppings. Heat stress in birds can be caused by high indoor temperatures and humidity, causing them to drink more and eat less in an attempt to control their body temperature. Heat stress has also been proven to disrupt intestinal integrity, resulting in a leaky and inflamed gut. Excess nutrients will increase renal outputs of water, while compromised gut integrity will diminish net water absorption from the intestinal tract, resulting in watery excreta.

Dietary Causes

Increased water consumption in birds attempt to maintain their electrolyte balance can lead to moist droppings if they consume too much potassium, magnesium, sodium, sulphate, or chloride in their meal or water. Mineral concentrations in the water should be examined on a regular basis to assure that there hasn't been a mixing error in the feed. Diarrhea can also be caused by poor quality or rancid fat. Furthermore, certain feed ingredients, notably those high in Non-Starch Polysaccharides (NSP) including wheat, barley, and rye, are frequently linked to wetter and more viscous excreta because these components trap water and prevent it from being reabsorbed. It is usual practise to utilise commercially available NSP-degrading enzymes in diets rich in these feed components.

Mycotoxins

Mycotoxins can also be found in mouldy feeds and feed additives. Mycotoxins, which are noxious fungal metabolites produced by common mold found in many poultry diets, can directly affect gut integrity, resulting in lower dietary nutrient, absorption and digestion as well as increased intestinal barrier permeability, which can contribute to damp litter. In addition, some mycotoxins, such as ochratoxins, can harm the kidneys and produce diuresis.

Pathogenic Causes

The most common disease linked to increased diarrhoea is coccidiosis, which is caused by protozoan parasites of the genus *Eimeria*. Coccidial infection, which can occur naturally or as a result of low-level introduction through live coccidiosis immunisation, can damage the intestinal epithelium, allowing bacteria to leak into the intestinal lumen. Furthermore, plasma protein leakage can provide a rich food substrate for *Clostridium perfringens* to use for growth and toxin synthesis, resulting in necrotic enteritis.

Pathogenic bacteria, such as *E. coli*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, and spirochaetes, as well as many viruses, including adenovirus, coronavirus, reovirus, and rotavirus, have all been implicated in diarrhoea. [14]

Factors associated with footpad dermatitis

Materials used for bedding

When it comes to raising broilers to market age, litter management is crucial. It is used for thermal insulation, moisture absorption, and ground protection. and also, as bedding material which is good moisture absorbent and also has reasonable

drying time. Litter is a term that refers to a mixture of bedding material, faeces, and moist. Various materials have been investigated for moisture absorption, caking, and bird performance in order to be used as broiler litter. The compression of litter layers into a single damp layer on the very top of the bedding material is referred to as caking. The moisture and faeces are frequently held in the litter by this thick, dense layer. As a result, removing caked litter between flocks is a typical management strategy, resulting in drier floors and better air quality for the next flock. Pine shavings were the best-performing substance, followed by the following: rice hulls, ground corncobs, stump chips, pine sawdust, bark and chips, pine bark, and clay. The most important factor was suggested to be differences in particle size of these materials. As long as the particle size was smaller than 1 in, there were no changes in paw quality or performance between hay, bark, and wood chip litter (2.5 cm). Pine shavings have been found to have lower FPD scores in broilers than straw. Some litter materials, particle size has been investigated as a contributing factor in the development of FPD.

Bird welfare

Foot, hock, and breast burns-lesions are a concern for bird welfare since they are the signs of housing conditions and the general well-being of the birds. Birds with severe lesions may lose weight as a result of pain-induced decreases feed intake.

Microbial factor

Staphylococcus aureus and other pathogens may be able to enter through these lesions. The most serious problem with FPD is that it could provide a pathway for microorganisms to enter the bloodstream and settle in the leg joints, causing leg weakness in older turkeys.

Paw health

Paw health refers to the overall health of the foot, including toes and footpad. A variety of factors, including heredity, environmental factors, nutrition, and bedding materials showed to affect paw health.

Litter Moisture

Litter moisture can be affected by a number of factors, including stocking density, ventilation, and drinker design. The moisture content in the litter is a crucial determinant in the development of FPD. Ulceration of broiler foot appears to be caused mainly by moist litter. Turkeys reared on wet litter exhibit greater rates of FPD than those raised on dry litter, similar to broilers. Constantly standing in damp litter softens the footpad and makes it more susceptible to damage, putting the bird at risk of getting FPD. The severity of FPD was reversed by drying out the litter and shifting the birds from wet to dry litter.

Drinker Management

Drinker design can influence the overall wetness of the litter and, as a result, the prevalence of FPD. The prevalence of FPD was higher in flocks reared on small drinker cups than in flocks reared on nipple drinkers. Small water cups have been found to have a lower incidence of FPD in turkeys than bell drinkers. Nipple drinkers with drip cups were the most efficient and produced better litter than nipple drinkers alone or bell drinkers. Wetter floors are caused by drinkers that are

too low or have the water pressure set too high. Leaky drinkers can be caused by biofilm or other particles in water lines, resulting in increased litter moisture. Water leakage can be reduced by cleansing and disinfecting the water pipes on a regular basis. This will keep the litter drier and of higher quality, resulting in better paw and hock health.

Depth of the litter

The occurrence of FPD in broilers was found to be unaffected by litter substance; instead, litter depth appeared to have a greater impact. Flocks raised on a thin layer (5 cm), A comparable study in France found that high-quality flocks were raised on thin layers of litter, and that adding high quantities of litter could be a risk factor for FPD, though it wasn't clear whether this was due to degrading litter conditions. FPD was less common in broilers reared on a deeper litter than in those reared on a thin layer. This shows that the depth of the litter may be a significant factor in foot health.

Nutrient factors

Vitamin and amino acid deficiencies in growing birds' diets, such as biotin, riboflavin, methionine, and cystine, have been associated with an increased risk of FPD. FPD lesions have been observed in turkeys fed biotin-deficient diets. Biotin supplementation reduced FPD in turkey poults fed with the diets lacking in riboflavin and biotin, but not riboflavin supplementation. The addition of riboflavin to turkey meals reduced dermatitis in the young birds. Poults fed with biotin-deficient diet developed severe dermatitis of the feet and around the head. Biotin supplementation was observed to have no effect on FPD in the poults.

Supplementation of vitamin and minerals

The structural components of the skin have been shown to be affected by nutrients such as biotin, riboflavin, pantothenic acid, and sulphur amino acids. The addition of vitamins and trace minerals did not significantly reduce FPD, leading to the conclusion that factors other than nutrition might be involved. Footpad dermatitis in young poults has been associated with a lack of methionine, although adding sulphate and cystine to the diet had little effect on the condition. Footpad condition was never fully corrected with the addition of methionine, but contact of the bird's feet with the excreta was suggested to play a major role in FPD. Supplementation of broiler diets with a zinc amino acid complex and found no significant difference in FPD scores in males, but did notice a decrease in lesions in females.

Seasonal variation

The time of year in which flocks are grown has been identified as a role in the occurrence of FPD. Dermatitis is more common in the winter than in the summer, and footpad condition has a direct correlation to RH both within and outside the broiler house.

There was an increase in paw lesions when outdoor RH levels increased throughout the winter months. When comparing winter flocks to summer flocks, an increase in the incidence of hock lesions has been observed.

Electrolyte Imbalance

Dietary salt content had a direct effect on the extent of footpad lesions, with higher levels of salt causing more severe dermatitis. Birds on high-salt diets exhibited more moisture in their faeces, resulting in poor litter conditions. With the increase in salt concentration, a decrease in both body weight and FPD, showing that body size is a risk factor for the development of lesions. [15]

Prevention and Treatment

Punica granatum peel aqueous extract may include bio-active elements that are active against diarrhoea, which could explain its traditional use for gastrointestinal diseases. In folk medicine pomegranate hulls are used as a well-known remedy in form of decoction for treating diarrhoea and dysentery. [16,17]

Acacia nilotica showed action on castor oil, magnesium sulphate induced diarrhoea and also produced antimicrobial effect, this evidence supported the ethnomedicinal use of acacia bark for treatment of diarrhoea. [18]

Holarrhena antidysenterica belongs to the family Apocynaceae which is known to have medicinal properties of its stem bark, leaves and seeds according to ayurveda. Traditionally *H. antidysenterica* has been used to treat diseases like dysentery, diarrhoea and helminthic disorders. Aqueous and alcoholic bark extracts are active against enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC), *Salmonella enteritidis*, *Shigella flexneri* and *Shigella boydii*. Aqueous and methanolic leaf extracts of *H. antidysenterica* were known to inhibit the growth of diarrhoeal pathogens *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Vibrio alginolyticus* and *Vibrio cholera*. [19,20]

Conclusion

This review is conducted to provide comprehensive information on wet litter associated problems in the poultry with its causative factors, disease models to evaluate the wet litter, prevention and treatment of the wet litter. Wet litter is a multifactorial problem, hence effective measures are necessary for prevention of wet litter. There are various herbs used in the management of wet litter like *Punica granatum*, *Acacia nilotica*, *Holarrhena antidysenterica* etc., which are used in the prevention and treatment of wet litter.

Acknowledgements

Authors thanks Dean Dr. Bharath and Dr. Anbu Faculty of Pharmacy, Ramaiah University of Applied Science, Bangalore and Karnataka, India.

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts of interest among the authors

References

- [1] S. F. Bilgili, J. B. Hess, J. P. Blake, K. S. Macklin, B. Saenmahayak and J. L. Sibley, "Influence of bedding material on footpad dermatitis in broiler chickens" *Journal of Applied Poultry Research* 18, no. 3, (2009), pp. 583-589.
- [2] M. W. Dunlop, J. McAuley, P. J. Blackall, and R. M. Stuetz. "Water activity of poultry litter: Relationship to moisture content during a grow-out" *Journal of Environmental Management* 172, (2016), pp. 201-206.
- [3] S. R. Collett. "Nutrition and wet litter problems in poultry" *Animal feed science and technology* 173, no. 1-2, (2012), pp. 65-75.
- [4] M. W. Dunlop, A. F. Moss, P. J. Groves, S. J. Wilkinson, R. M. Stuetz and P. H. Selle, "The multidimensional causal factors of 'wet litter' in chicken-meat production" *Science of the Total Environment* 562, (2016), pp. 766-776.
- [5] I. C. De Jong, H. Gunnink and J. Van Harn, "Wet litter not only induces footpad dermatitis but also reduces overall welfare, technical performance, and carcass yield in broiler chickens" *Journal of Applied Poultry Research* 23, no. 1, (2014), pp. 51-58.
- [6] E. V. Hoeven-Hangoor, C. J. Rademaker, N. D. Paton, M. W. A. Verstegen and W. H. Hendriks, "Evaluation of free water and water activity measurements as functional alternatives to total moisture content in broiler excreta and litter samples" *Poultry Science* 93, no. 7, (2014), pp. 1782-1792.
- [7] S. T. Tran, M. E. Bowman and T. K. Smith, "Effects of a silica-based feed supplement on performance, health, and litter quality of growing turkeys" *Poultry Science* 94, no. 8, (2015), pp. 1902-1908.
- [8] E. M. Shepherd and B. D. Fairchild, "Footpad dermatitis in poultry" *Poultry science* 89, no. 10, (2010), pp. 2043-2051.
- [9] S. Swiatkiewicz, A. A. Wlosek and D. Jozefiak, "The nutrition of poultry as a factor affecting litter quality and foot pad dermatitis—an updated review" *Journal of Animal Physiology and Animal Nutrition* 101, no. 5, (2017), pp. e14-e20.
- [10] B. A. Slominski, "Recent advances in research on enzymes for poultry diets" *Poultry Science* 90, no. 9, (2011), pp. 2013-2023.
- [11] M. Casewell, C. Friis, E. Marco, P. McMullin and I. Phillips, "The European ban on growth-promoting antibiotics and emerging

- consequences for human and animal health" *Journal of antimicrobial chemotherapy* 52, no. 2, (2003), pp. 159-161.
- [12] S. Marimuthu, B. Balasubramanian, R. Selvam and P. D'Souza, "Evaluation of a polyherbal formulation for the management of wet litter in broiler chickens: Implications on performance parameters, cecal moisture level, and footpad lesions" *Journal of Advanced Veterinary and Animal Research* 6, no. 4, (2019), pp. 536.
- [13] E. V. Hoeven-Hangoor, I. B. Van de Linde, N. D. Paton, M. W. A. Verstegen and W. H. Hendriks, "Effect of different magnesium sources on digesta and excreta moisture content and production performance in broiler chickens." *Poultry science* 92, no. 2, (2013), pp.382-391.
- [14] M. W. Dunlop, A. F. Moss, P. J. Groves, S. J. Wilkinson, R. M. Stuetz and P. H. Selle, "The multidimensional causal factors of 'wet litter' in chicken-meat production" *Science of the Total Environment* 562, (2016), pp. 766-776.
- [15] E. M. Shepherd and B. D. Fairchild, "Footpad dermatitis in poultry" *Poultry science* 89, no. 10, (2010), pp. 2043-2051.
- [16] E. Lansky, S. Shubert and I. Neeman, "Pharmacological and therapeutic properties of pomegranate" *Production, processing and marketing of pomegranate in the Mediterranean region: Advances in research and technology*, (2000), pp. 231-235.
- [17] E. Y. Qnais, A. S. Elokda, Y. Y. Abu Ghalyun and F. A. Abdulla, "Antidiarrheal Activity of the Aqueous extract of *Punica granatum*. (Pomegranate) peels" *Pharmaceutical Biology* 45, no. 9, (2007), pp. 715-720.
- [18] A. Misar, R. Bhagat and A. M. Mujumdar, "Antidiarrhoeal activity of *Acacia nilotica* Willd. bark methanol extract" *Hindustan antibiotics bulletin* 49, no. 1-4, (2007), pp. 14-20.
- [19] A. H. Gilani, A. Khan, A. U. Khan, S. Bashir, N. Rehman and S. R. Mandukhail, "Pharmacological basis for the medicinal use of *Holarrhena antidysenterica* in gut motility disorders" *Pharmaceutical biology* 48, no. 11, (2010), pp. 1240-1246.
- [20] D. K. Sharma, V. K. Gupta, S. Kumar, V. Joshi, R. S. K. Mandal, A. G. B. Prakash and M. Singh, "Evaluation of antidiarrheal activity of ethanolic extract of *Holarrhena antidysenterica* seeds in rats" *Veterinary World* 8, no. 12, (2015), pp. 1392.